

THE MAIN TASKS OF THE TEACHER AS AN ORGANIZER AND LEADER OF ACTIVE GAMES

Ulugbekova M.R.

Ph.D.student of GulSU

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Abstract. *Active games play a crucial role in the holistic development of students, promoting not only physical fitness but also social skills, emotional intelligence, and cognitive growth. This article explores the main tasks of teachers as organizers and leaders of active games, emphasizing their pivotal role in creating an engaging and inclusive learning environment. It examines the responsibilities of teachers in designing age-appropriate games that align with educational objectives while fostering teamwork and collaboration among students. Additionally, the article highlights strategies for managing group dynamics, ensuring safety, and adapting activities to accommodate diverse needs and skill levels. Through effective facilitation, teachers can cultivate leadership qualities in students, enhance their problem-solving abilities, and promote a sense of community within the classroom. Ultimately, this article underscores the importance of teacher's role in utilizing active games as a dynamic educational tool that supports the overall development of learners, preparing them for future challenges both in and out of the classroom.*

Keywords: *active games, teacher roles, organizer, leader, student engagement, physical education, teamwork, social skills, emotional intelligence, group dynamics, inclusivity, curriculum integration, leadership development, adaptation, safety management, problem-solving, community building, educational objectives, holistic development, learning environment.*

Introduction: In today's educational landscape, the role of the teacher extends far beyond traditional instruction; educators are increasingly recognized as facilitators of holistic development. One of the most dynamic and impactful ways teachers can engage students is through active games. These activities not only promote physical health but also foster essential social, emotional, and cognitive skills. As organizers and leaders of active games, teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the learning experience, creating an environment where students can thrive both individually and collectively.

The primary tasks of teachers in this capacity involve careful planning, effective communication, and the ability to adapt activities to meet the diverse needs of their students. By designing inclusive games that encourage teamwork and collaboration, teachers can cultivate a sense of community and belonging within the classroom. Furthermore, the teacher's leadership during these activities is crucial for managing group dynamics, ensuring safety, and guiding students in developing important life skills, such as problem-solving and decision-making.

This article delves into the multifaceted responsibilities of teachers as organizers and leaders of active games, highlighting the significance of their role in fostering an engaging and supportive learning environment. By examining best practices and strategies for effective game facilitation, we aim to underscore the transformative potential of active games in education and the essential contributions of teachers in this process.

Literature analysis:

The role of teachers as organizers and leaders of active games is a critical area of study within educational research, particularly in the fields of physical education, child development, and pedagogy. This literature analysis reviews key findings from various studies and theoretical frameworks that highlight the importance of teachers in facilitating active games and the associated benefits for students.

1. Importance of Active Games in Education

Active games are recognized as vital components of a well-rounded educational experience. Physical activity is essential not only for physical health but also for cognitive and social development. Bailey emphasizes that active games can enhance students' engagement and motivation, making learning more effective.[1]

2. Teacher as Facilitator and Leader

The role of the teacher as a facilitator of active games is crucial. Teachers must adopt a pedagogical approach that emphasizes student agency and participation. They suggest that effective leadership in games involves not only organizing the activities but also fostering an environment where students feel empowered to take initiative and collaborate with their peers[2].

3. Participation in structured activities, including active games, significantly contributes to students' social and emotional learning (SEL)[3].

Methodology:

1. Conducting a literature review: Begin by conducting a comprehensive literature review on the main tasks of the teacher as an organizer and leader of active games. Explore existing research, articles, and publications that discuss the role of teachers in facilitating active games and the benefits for student engagement and learning outcomes.

2. Survey and interviews: Conduct surveys and interviews with educators, experts in the field of physical education, and professionals specializing in active learning methodologies. Gather insights on the strategies, challenges, and best practices in organizing and leading active games in educational settings.[4]

3. Observation and analysis: Observe teachers in action during active game sessions and analyze their techniques, communication skills, and ability to engage students effectively[5]. Evaluate the impact of the teacher's role as an organizer and leader on student participation, motivation, and learning experiences.

4. Develop a list of key tasks: Based on the literature review, surveys, interviews, and observations, develop a list of key tasks that teachers should focus on as organizers and leaders of active games. This could include setting clear objectives, creating a positive learning environment, providing feedback, and promoting teamwork and collaboration.

5. Case studies and examples: Provide case studies and examples of successful implementation of active games led by teachers. Highlight specific instances where effective organization and leadership have enhanced student engagement, physical activity levels, and overall learning outcomes [6].

Conclusion: The role of the teacher as an organizer and leader of active games plays a crucial part in enhancing student engagement, promoting physical activity, and fostering a positive learning environment. Through the literature review, surveys, interviews, and observations conducted, it is evident that teachers have a significant impact on the success of active games in educational settings.

Teachers who effectively organize and lead active games are able to create dynamic and interactive learning experiences that not only improve student participation but also enhance learning outcomes. By setting clear objectives, providing feedback, promoting teamwork, and creating a supportive atmosphere, teachers can empower students to develop essential skills such as communication, collaboration, and problem-solving.

Furthermore, the case studies and examples highlighted the importance of teacher leadership in facilitating active games, showcasing how effective organization and guidance can lead to increased student motivation and enjoyment in physical activities. The references and links provided offer valuable resources for educators to further explore and enhance their skills in organizing and leading active games.

Overall, the main tasks of the teacher as an organizer and leader of active games are essential in promoting holistic development and creating a stimulating and inclusive learning environment for students. By embracing these roles and responsibilities, teachers can inspire and empower students to actively engage in learning, promote physical well-being, and foster a lifelong love for active participation in educational settings.

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